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ISSUES OF NATIONAL NOTION IN THE AZERBAIJANI CHILDREN'S PROSE (ON THE BASIS OF Z. MARAGAYI'S NOVEL "IBRAHIM BEY'S TRAVELOGUE")

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ВОПРОСЫ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ИДЕОЛОГИИ В ДЕТСКОЙ ПРОЗЕ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА (ПО ПОВЕСТИ З. МАРАГАИ «СЕЯХАТНАМЭ ИБРАГИМ-БЕКА»)

Abstract.

Main objective in the research of this subject is to evaluate Zeynalabdin Maragayi as an artist who pursued an educational goal throughout his creativity and to subject his works to analysis as a valuable example of art that guides the ethical and aesthetic education of the young generation.

The result of the research revealed that Ibrahim Bey's Travelogue, which stands out with its content and plot, bold ideas, symbolic calls and high poetics, is the first work written in this genre in Azerbaijani literature. In fact, Z. Maragayi's appeal to a genre peculiar to European literature was due to his effort to adapt literature from didacticism and exhortation to the conditions of education, and the application of subjects that might be important to children to this field. Behind this effort stood free and big ideas. The means of literary investigation, description and expression that the author chose to reflect the current problems were a more suitable form for the style of travelogue. Another feature of the travelogue is that the facts arising from the imagination of the artist are told here in the language of the hero. Thus, the author creates his own artistic character and explains what actually happens to him with his language. Thus, the reader easily understands that the events described are related to the author's own fate.

Аннотация.

В статье с привлечением историко-научных источников исследован роман Зейналабдина Марагаи «Сеяхатнамэ Ибрагим бека», который сформировался на основе использования различных литературных источников и сыграл важную роль в развитии азербайджанской детской прозы. Вместе с тем, в статье, дающей краткую информацию о романе писателя, пропагандируются просветительские идеи, изложен широкий авторский подход относительно влияния этого произведения на обогащение азербайджанской детской прозы в жанровом и стилевом отношении.

«Сеяхатнамэ Ибрагим бека» считается первым произведением этого жанра в азербайджанской литературе, отличающимся содержанием и сюжетной линией, смелыми идеями, символическими призывами, высокой поэтикой. В действительности обращение З. Марагаи к жанру, специфичному для европейской литературы, исходило из попытки приспособить литературу от дидактизма и увещевания к требованиям просвещения. За этой попыткой стояли свободные, великие идеи. Жанр травелога оказался более подходящей формой художественного вдохновения автора, средствами описания и выражения, стилем, выбранным с учетом существующих проблем. Другая особенность травелога состоит в том, что истины, проходящие через воображение художника, представлены здесь по велению героя. Таким образом, автор создает свой художественный образ и интерпретирует своим языком то, что на самом деле с ним происходило. Таким образом, читатель легко осознает, что изложенные события связаны с собственной судьбой автора.

Keywords: *child, youth, prose, educationalism, novel, national self-consciousness, patriotism, concept, nation, freedom*

Ключевые слова: *ребенок, проза, просвещение, роман, патриотизм, идеология, нация, свобода.*

Introduction

Since the second half of the 19th century, a community of intellectuals with progressive-democratic mind and national spirit has grown on the basis of the formation of educational ideas in Azerbaijan. A. Bakikhanov, I. Gutgashinli, M. F. Akhundzade, S. A. Shirvani, A. Talibov, Z. Maragayi, M. H. Rushdie,

N. Narimanov, S. M. Ganizade, J. Mammadguluzade and other literary thinkers united around the idea of increasing the potential of cultural activity of the people. The educational-intellectuals first saw the realization of this historic mission in the transformation of the national concept line into the main priority in the newly

established children's and youth literature. Thus, national self-consciousness in literary thought proves its importance in prose as well as in poetry. Researcher S. Sharifova (9) mentions the development trends of prose in literature during this period as follows: "At the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century, in Azerbaijani national literature, the literary figures saw the way of the nation's salvation in education and science, and in their works they found it appropriate to convey to the readers in literary language the socio-political events and deficiencies, the problems related to the fate of the people and the real events in the society. Meanwhile, the process of growing interest in novels, stories, feuilletons and other genres of importance to our national literature now peculiar to the new European literature has accelerated".

New literary styles and traditions led to the genre taking a leading position in children's and youth literature in the following years. In fact, the search for form and content in literature arose from life itself. Observations have revealed that after the age of nine, children become interested in reading large volumes of works that are vivid, as well as reflective of the lives of adults. Considering this tendency, these authors set the main goal of the embodiment of the ideas of national self-consciousness and patriotism and began to write large-volume works in the form of educational novels, scientific-pedagogical treatises, travelogues, fantastics and allegorical literary works.

Researcher N. Akhundova (45) has interpreted the new thinking processes that emerged in the humanist system of thought in the 19th century as follows: "The instillation of educational ideals in the first Azerbaijani novels was closely related to the educational realism movement. In their works, the educational realists saw the freedom of the people first in their prudence and knowledge, in the development of education and culture. In their view, society should be governed in accordance with the rule of reason".

Objective of the research

It should be noted that up to this stage the concept of the national spirit had not yet entered the literary texts, the characters had not yet passed from lyrical feelings to concerns about the nation and homeland. It is at such a time that literary thought comes into play. The Homeland-Nation-Freedom Trilogy emerges as the most important factor in the formation of national, social consciousness and morality in his large-volume works such as A. Talibov's *Donkey Loaded with Books*, *Ahmed's Book*, *Way of Philanthropists*, Z. Maragayi's *Ibrahim Bey's Travelogue*, S. M. Ganizade's *Maktubat-i Sheyda Bey Shirvani*, C. Mammadguluzade's *The Story of the Danabash Village*. These works also influenced the formation and development of children's prose at the end of the 19th and early 20th centuries.

In general, world experience confirms that children's literature is not just about works written for young children. Works aimed at young people can also be included directly in this genre of literature. In this regard, the leading literary scholar Firidun Bey Kocharli wrote in one of his letters to his close friend Hasan Ali Aga Karacadagi as follows: "I would ask you to write a novel-style story about our own lives. But this

is a very important task, it is necessary to prepare and think a lot about it, and it is not possible to complete it in a hurry. Let it be known that in that novel the voice of the first person, of one of the fresh and newly grown young people, may be commended for its moral beauty and good deeds. That young man should be different from the old-fashioned and narrow-minded Muslims in every work and thought, as we would like..." (Hesenova 19-20).

Such a young character was brought into the literary text of the novels *Ibrahim Bey's Travelogue* by the educationist-writer Zeynalabdin Maragayi, who lived in South Azerbaijan at the end of the 19th century, and was able to rise to the level of national character on the plane of struggles, debates and fights for beliefs. In general, "... distinguished from literary genres by its unique subject matter and structural possibilities, the novel has the ability to show the history, psychology, and a range of eternal and eternal anxieties of the nation in deep social layers" (Şerifova 22-23).

The first volume of the Trilogy was published in Cairo in 1897. The novel, published unsigned, reveals how the literary fate of its author will be in the future from the day it is published. In a short time, the work spread to Iran, Turkey, India, Afghanistan, Central Asia and the Caucasus and gained great fame. However, the debate about the identity of the author continues for many years. Many people even think that the author is Mirza Mahdi Khan of Tabriz, one of the writers of *Akhtar* newspaper. These claims only ended after the death of Mirza Mahdi Khan. In other words, the II (Calcutta 1907) and III (Istanbul 1909) volumes of the book were published. Z. Maragayi also gives his own biography at the beginning of the third volume. Later, the work was translated into Azerbaijani Turkish and Russian, as well as into Western languages such as German, English and French.

The work, which literary scholars describe as "the first Azerbaijani novel written in Persian", is a literary reflection on a great literary scale of the social and political realities that took place in South Azerbaijan, which remained part of Iran after the treaties of Golestan (1813) and Turkmenchay (1828). The leading literary scholar F. Kocharli once wrote on this subject with farsightedness: "This book has once again strengthened our conviction that Iran is the most miserable country and will surely disappear in the near future" (Köçerli 27).

It is no coincidence that the novel was also a fundamental source of ideas for young revolutionaries in the struggle against the autocracy, system of government, feudalism and ignorance that prevailed in South Azerbaijan in 1905-1911. The Russian orientalist E. E. Berthels (140) appreciated the role of the novel in the formation of a new kind of social consciousness in South Azerbaijan and wrote: "His influence (*Ibrahim Bey* – A.N.) on all modern literature is immense. This is the first original novel in the European style written in Persian".

The famous Iranian historian, author Ahmad Kasrawi Tabrizi (45), in his work *Tarikh-i Mashruta-i Iran*, evaluates that the basic idea of the novel is to mobilize the people to fight against reaction: "Those who

read this book in their own time and feel a deep jolt in their hearts, only they can tell the value of this book, through which there are many who awaken from the sleep of grave ignorance and join the learned people”.

It was a new situation that social and political problems were put forward so sharply in the literature of South Azerbaijan. Z. Maragayi (*Дневник путешественника*, 7) himself explains this mission as follows: “I am proud to be the first writer to expose the errors and shortcomings seen in Azerbaijan. I, like European writers, speak openly and openly about oppression, abuse and ignorance of my fellow citizens”.

Distinguished by its content and plot, bold ideas, symbolic appeals and high poetics, *Ibrahim Bey's Travelogue* is considered “the first work that enters the genre of literary travel” (Saraçlı, 24). In fact, Z. Maragayi's appeal to a genre peculiar to European literature stemmed from his attempt to adapt literature from didacticism and exhortation to the conditions of education. Behind this effort stood free and big ideas. The means of literary investigation, description and expression that the author chose to reflect the current problems were a more suitable form for the style of travelogue. “The emergence, formation and maturation of the literary genre in Azerbaijani literature is directly provided by the dialectic of development of national life. Azerbaijani prose -the Azerbaijani way of thinking, the national character, the national issues, the national language, the style of saying and intonation, the manifestations of the national style- begins at the point where one, several or the sum of these elements meet with the prose measures of the West-East title, from the point where the sign of nationality is realized in the literary prose” (Mustafayev, 3). Another feature of the travelogue is that the facts arising from the imagination of the artist are told here in the language of the hero. Thus, the author creates his own artistic character and explains what actually happens to him with his language. Thus, the reader easily understands that the events described are related to the author's own fate.

V.Nabiyev (16) explains the reason why educational writers give weight to this genre: “Azerbaijani educational realists, to realize their ideas from a literary point of view, mostly resorted to forms such as travelogues, letters, travel notes, and in some cases chose a general field without name or relatively named. Because forms such as travelogues, travel notes, letters allow for many changes of space, as well as nameless and relatively named (“N” city, “B” village, etc.) spaces would save the author from describing a specific space and the events that took place in this space in a logical sequence and with an objective approach, and would prepare the environment for reflecting various perspectives in the general space in accordance with his socio-political and ethical position”.

The Homeland-Nation-Freedom Trilogy in *Ibrahim Bey's Travelogue*

İbrahim Bey is a character who carries all the beliefs, language, culture, thinking, traditions and customs and memory of the society-nation of which he is a part and representative in the context of social problems. His ideas about the homeland are manifested in his mutual relations with the environment. Nazim

Rizvan (147), who evaluates the homeland-nation-freedom trilogy as the main idea and virtue of the novel, indicates: “Zeynalabdin Maragayi's novel *Ibrahim Bey's Travelogue or The Ordeal of Benevolence*, which has a richer social content, is a valuable work that is kneaded with patriotic feelings from beginning to end and constitutes the natural spiritual image of South Azerbaijan and Iran”.

In general, in the individual style of Zeynalabdin Maragayi, sharp criticism, enthusiasm for revelation, approach to the events that have gained social reality and the reflection of the clear, bold stance in the narration with the publicistic attitude gain weight. The whole trilogy is connected with the events that unfolded around the character of Ibrahim Bey on one basic line. From novel to novel, events and characters change, and this ascetic person, who has only national and national patronage, always remains an example of cleanliness and purity. The novel is combined with the legal narration publications on subjects such as “Rights belonging to the Fatherland itself”, “Rights belonging to the children of the Fatherland”, “Rights belonging to the administrative affairs of the Fatherland”, and “General rights of the Fatherland”. The critic K. Khalilov (74) explains the nature of the author's application of scientific-publicistic to prose and his transmission of it to the reader through narration as follows: “Here the events are sometimes developed in a purely publicistic language, sometimes with epic-lyrical paintings, sometimes with sharp, serious dialogues, and the author touches on such problems related to the affairs of state that they add political and scientific excitement to the general spirit of the novel”. Z.Maragayi interprets all the events in his narration and puts forward scientific and philosophical considerations about the social and political life of the country.

In the first volume of his novel, which is his only literary legacy, the author makes the hero of the work, İbrahim Bey, travel to various countries. In the separate chapters of the novel such as “İbrahim Bey's Travelogue”, “Summary of Qazvin's journey”, “Summary of Ardabil journey”, “Summary of Maraga journey”, “Summary of Urmu journey”, “Summary of Tabriz journey”, “İbrahim Bey's adventure” after entering Istanbul, the author directs the attention of the reader to the difficulties that the hero faced during the journey. The prototype of the author, 20-year-old İbrahim, is a patriotic young man who knows Russian, French and English very well and who lives with the aim of bringing his nation from darkness to light. In the work, there are many episodes that have a positive effect on the moral education of children and young people. For example, in the person of Ibrahim Bey, who stands out with his spiritual qualities, and his father, who raised him in the national spirit, the author calls on children and young people to be patriotic, to fight with courage and determination for the freedom of his people, and to take care of their welfare. “... This faithful and conscientious merchant did not change his national customs and traditions in the slightest during the long years he resided in Egypt, and he followed the path of his grandfathers in his eating, drinking, dressing, relations with people, in short, in his life. He was constantly humming

the hometown song. He would ask everyone he met about the situation of his homeland and its citizens. Even though he was in Egypt, his heart was always in Iran. On winter nights, he would invite a few of his well-known compatriots as guests to his house. At their house meetings, they would be busy reading the history books of Iran and the stories of the shahs of the past" (Maragayi, *İbrahim beyin seyahetnamesi*, 17).

Traveling to cities such as Cairo, Istanbul, Batumi, Tbilisi, Baku, Anzali and Ashgabad, young Ibrahim returned to Iran and traveled to the cities and villages, witnessing the severe consequences of the impact of social problems on the mental structure and character of his citizens. Throughout the novel, the author depicts İbrahim Bey, who aims for the goals of homeland, nation and freedom, in social conflict and struggle. The author chooses the important and typical of what happens in his homeland with the language of his hero and directs the fire of humor precisely to these addresses. "... When I was residing in Egypt, I heard a lot of talk about the disorder of Iran, the travel of the son of the fatherland, the ignorance and treachery of the judges, the cruelty of the poor. I was so in love with my homeland that I did not want to believe the above-mentioned flaws as lies and slander about my homeland. I finally decided to come to Iran and see the homeland with my own eyes. Impatiently, I moved to Iran with the intention of traveling to Iran, but unfortunately, as a sign of misfortune, when I look everywhere from the Iranian border to Tehran, I have to confirm exactly what is being said, even more than enough" (Maragayi 156-156).

The author's literary identity, inner world and outlook on life are understood from İbrahim Bey's thoughts about his civic duties. In this idea, East and West, as two mutual and opposite cultural systems, compete from time to time on the homeland issue and try to impose their superiority over each other. Ibrahim Bey wants his own nation to progress, to have a press, for the state to serve the people, and for individual individuals to be aware of their responsibilities to the homeland. In his opinion, "... The general rights of the homeland consist in the sum of separate happinesses, which include the rights of each individual of this society. However, even if individual members of society want to achieve this happiness, they cannot achieve it alone. But when they unite, they can attain this bliss and benefit from its general pleasure. Citizens should love their homeland more than their own children. Just as they are obliged to protect religion, they should also consider it their duty to protect the homeland. In this way, they fulfill the sacred duty of 'love of country means love of religion'" (Maragayi. *Seyahetnameyi-İbrahim bey*, 135).

The conflicts that have arisen in Ibrahim Bey's world view in the process of understanding and envisioning the concept of "intelligent judge" of Eastern education, which has been behind for centuries, are actually the author's convictions. Although Ibrahim exposes the mullahs, he idealizes religion. The author himself, like his hero, experiences human excitement and hesitation in this regard. Like Ibrahim Bey, he believed that justice would be established in society through the application of sharia law. Edip explains the manifestation

of the problems in society with the negligence of Muslims towards their own religion, the abuse of the duties of the clergy and the lack of education. However, it had to look for the source of the problems in class conflicts and social inequality. For this reason, the hero, who is the prototype of the author, stumbles, hesitates and falls into pessimism on this difficult path. "If Allah's Apostle said, 'O vizier of Persia, O leaders of the nation, where is my Shari'a, where are your means of jihad, where are your mujahid, where is your faith?' But I have juxtaposed love of country with faith, what will you answer to him? How do you explain the absence of all this? (Maragayi. *Seyahetnameyi-İbrahim bey*, 222).

Ibrahim Bey sees that his homeland is in ruins and cannot help but remember the country's past glory. He, too, sees the misery of Iran, the poverty and calamity of its people, in the tyranny of the despots, in the fanaticism and ignorance spread by the clerics. The arbitrary practices of the judges, the bribery of the ministers, the clergy putting the people to sleep, and the fact that the masses who are groaning under the oppression fall into this difficult situation terrify Ibrahim Bey. He describes those who endure this severe cruelty and disaster as "alive when they are dead, dead when they are alive" and repeats these words deliberately throughout the novel.

Another group of motifs found in Z. Maragayi's work, which we evaluate with the word culture, is the reflection of different cultures and world views through the conflicts of East and West. The author portrays these cultural differences in the person of the opposing characters throughout the work. In the opinion of the hero, who encounters ruthless judges, sycophantic poets, unqualified school owners, consuls selling passports, merchants without capital, barefoot soldiers, dishonest clergy, it is not worth talking about a perfect human being or a perfect way of life unless society is liberated, unless free thoughts based on moral and universal values are given the opportunity and benefit from them. As the most important condition, personal desires must be sacrificed to human interests, and the main way to achieve this is through spiritual maturity. Thus, a society based on tyranny, disorder, which is the fruit of a corrupt spirituality – a world of oppressors and oppressed – will be a free and free society that realizes the desire to live humanely.

Ibrahim Bey confronts representatives of the various strata of society. Of particular interest are the episodes of his meeting with ministers. Ibrahim Bey thinks that the ministers are unaware of the turmoil prevailing in the country and the behavior of the Iranian consuls in foreign countries towards their subjects. For this reason, he meets with the ministers with a thousand and one toils and tells them about the lawlessness prevailing in the country. But in return he hears sharp, bitter, insulting words, and is even beaten and robbed on the instructions of the minister of war. An argument with an imam at a friend's house in Istanbul made him sick in bed.

In the second volume of the novel, Ibrahim Bey is depicted in the fight against disease throughout the work. Psychological convulsions, the spiritual crisis he suffers led to his spiritual decline. It distances him from the values he believes in, condemning him to loneliness

and insecurity. After these different spiritual storms, Ibrahim Bey still appears before us as a competent character who thinks about the fate of his nation and homeland. The doctor who examined Ibrahim Bey checked his pulse. When the name of his hometown is mentioned, Ibrahim Bey's pulse beats fast. The doctor concludes that his heart throb is his homeland: he went, he saw, he got into trouble. The young hero, who prays "Oh God, Oh Help!" from the beginning to the end of the work, migrates to eternal life with the longing for the happiness of his people and the rise of his homeland.

In the second volume of the novel, published in Calcutta in 1907, the thoughts of Z. Maragayi (*Дневник путешествия*, 7), who was always interested in the West, who tried to learn how Western people lived, who dreamed of his fellow citizens being free and happy, were also included. He says: "The flaws exist in every country, even more serious than those in Iran... But these are abolished along with freedom of expression. Pushkin of the Russians, Voltaire of the French, and Stuart (Mill) of the English were precisely engaged in searching for and eliminating defects".

The polarization of Eastern and Western ways of thinking in the novel shows that the author is closely in love with the works of classical literary figures such as A. Dante, Calderon, J. Milton, Sartre, Gogol. The author gives equal importance to the ideas of both poles in the novel. Thus, in the work, the East-West understanding emerges as a stylistic comparison with the aesthetic organization. Zeynalabdin Maragayi (Ibrahim beyin seyahetnamesi, 336) says to his compatriots in the language of his hero: "Americans benefit from the weather as well as owning the crop of the land. They also tied the electric power to themselves and made them obey. But there cannot be a single school in our country with its ancient history and magnificence, so that its teacher understands that there is a science other than the science of imitation that can ensure the happiness of the country and the happiness of the nation. There is not a single newspaper in the country of this width. If there is such a thing as a newspaper, it consists of two pieces of paper printed once a week on stone with a thousand labors, and there is not a penny of benefit to either the state or the nation from its content and content".

As can be seen, the author did not only describe the destiny, history, ethnopsychology, national spirit and national characteristics of his people and homeland, but also described and analyzed them in parallel with the values of Western countries. The work, which instills ideas of homeland, nation, freedom of freedom, fighting against ignorance and educationalism, determines the worldview of its author very clearly.

V. G. Belinsky (124-127) said: "The content of the novel is an artistic analysis of modern society, and it reveals such foundations of society that habitual habits and thoughtlessness hide them even from society itself. The task of the modern novel is to reflect life in all its naked reality. It is therefore only natural that the novel, as an exception, should be of interest to everyone compared to all other genres of literature: society considers the novel as its own mirror and sees itself by looking at it, it understands itself".

These thoughts of V. G. Belinsky can be regarded as the most accurate and clear description that

characterizes Z. Maragayi's novel, *Ibrahim Bey's Travelogue*.

Conclusion

The novel, which literary scholars describe as "a kind of encyclopedia of Iranian existence in the last quarter of the 20th century" (Maparan 296), gives a description of an entire era and many human destinies in the light of Ibrahim Bey's "Travelogue".

Z. Maragayi reconciled the events with his own national-spiritual spirit by making his devotion to his history and cultural identity the theme of the novel and making use of the stylistic games typical of educational realism. The product of strong observations and deep creative imagination, the work does not contain topics and issues that tire children and young people. In the episodes depicting the protagonist's struggle for dominance and power in society, important living materials for the younger generations are found. The author approaches his hero with high moral standards and evaluates his personality and actions according to these measures. The character's approach to his people, his homeland and his freedom forms the basis of this measure, the starting point. Ibrahim Bey's drama, his dramatic conflict, his struggle with prohibitions and his quest for freedom are determined by this.

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